

**THE ROLE OF INNOVATIONS IN THE DEVELOPMENT
OF THE COUNTRY'S ECONOMY AND DIRECTIONS FOR USING
THEM EFFECTIVELY**

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Abstract. In this article, the economic potential of our country is analyzed through the macroeconomic indicator of gross domestic product. The process of improving the economy through innovative achievements in Uzbekistan and the number of innovations were studied by sectors, and directions for their wider implementation were indicated.

Keywords. Economic potential, gross domestic product, innovation, technological innovation.

Introduction

The role of countries in the world community is determined by many factors. Among these factors, their economic potential is one of the most important. In this regard, in the process of analyzing the economic potential of countries, it is necessary to pay special attention to the amount of goods and services created there, that is, the macroeconomic indicator of GDP. When studying the value of this indicator over the years, special attention should be paid to the fact that the value of the goods and services created is measured at base prices. Because the nominal GDP does not allow a correct assessment of the development trend of the country's economic potential.

Analysis and results

Although the value of this indicator in the Republic of Uzbekistan remained almost unchanged in 2019, 2020 and 2021, in 2022 compared to 2018 it increased by 27.5 billion US dollars, i.e. by 52% (Figure 1).

Figure 1. GDP of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2018-2022 (in billion US dollars)¹

In addition, the analysis of the share and amount of net taxes on goods, services and products in the country's GDP is important in assessing the economic potential of countries (Figure 2).

Figure 2. GDP of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2018-2022 (at current prices, trillion soums)²

It is known from the above table that the goods created and services provided in our country have been constantly increasing. Net taxes on products decreased significantly in 2020, despite the increase in the taxable object. This is a clear example of the opportunities given by our government in order to reduce the losses that enterprises may suffer during the pandemic.

It is extremely important to make full use of the possibilities of effective use of the resources available in our country in order to improve the well-being of the population by ensuring a high level of development in all areas of our country. For this, it is necessary to create and implement innovations in all fields, and this practice is becoming one of the global goals all over the world. In this regard, the USA, Germany, Japan and other developed countries are achieving a high level of efficiency through innovation policies.

It should be noted that special attention is being paid to the issue of improving the economy through innovative achievements in Uzbekistan. In particular, the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On organizational measures for the implementation of the innovative development strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2022-2026" dated 06.07.2022 No. PQ-307 was adopted, according to which a number of reforms are defined as priorities[1].

A lot of tasks are set within the different directions of this strategy. In particular, as priorities in the 6th direction of the strategy, the creation of an evaluation system for the scientific activity of scientific and higher education organizations and the creation of new scientific development and technology projects by scientific and higher education organizations to innovative business entities based on their orders. The goals of developing proposals for providing vouchers for financing, supporting the inventive initiatives of

¹Formed by the author based on the information of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan

²Formed by the author based on the information of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan

secondary school students, developing a personnel training system for managing, commercializing and protecting innovative projects in cooperation with leading foreign universities.

According to the State Statistics Committee, by the end of 2021, the number of organizations that introduced technological innovations in our country was 1098, the main part of them, that is, 669 in the manufacturing industry, 274 and it is directed to the development of other types of economic activity. The state of total technological innovations in the cross-section of economic activities is shown in the following diagram:

Figure 3. Status of introduced technological innovations in the section of economic activities (units)³

From the information given in the above chart, it can be concluded that the main part of the total technological innovations was used in the manufacturing industry, and as a result, the economic potential of industrial enterprises increased. However, health and social services, education, and information and communication are among the lowest in terms of implementation. This means that it is necessary to pay special attention to these areas.

If we analyze the application of these technological innovations according to the number of regions, the highest rate belongs to the city of Tashkent and Navoi regions, while the Fergana region ranks fifth with the rate of application of 105 innovations. is occupying the mother. The regions that introduced the least number of innovations were the Republic of Karakalpakstan, Andijan and Khorezm regions. By the end of 2021, the amount of the above-mentioned technological innovations in our country in the total regional section was as follows (Fig. 4):

³Formed by the author based on the information of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Figure 4. The number of organizations that introduced technological innovations in the region⁴

Conclusion and suggestions

There is a huge resource base in our country. In order to use these opportunities wisely, we need to open a wide path to innovation. In this regard, we found it necessary to perform the following tasks:

1. Funding is the foundation of every activity. Because of this, first of all, we need to pay attention to sufficient financing of innovative activities. For this, it is necessary to allocate sufficient funds to provide preferential loans, to support the creation of innovations from the state and local budgets.

2. Legal protection of innovative activity by the state. By creating a strong legal framework, with adequate funding, intellectual property owners will feel safe and comfortable, and the level of migration of researchers abroad will decrease.

3. It is necessary to support innovators financially and morally, that is, to give them various incentives, gifts, to organize various events, to give them the opportunity to relax, and to give them free passes to sanatoriums.

4. We need to accelerate the transition to Industry 4.0. In this, modern smart technologies of the production and supply chain, big data base (Big Data), artificial intelligence (AI), large-scale car to car model (M2M), internet of things (IoT), "cloud" computing (Cloud computing) and other technologies, we need to digitize the industry, turn enterprises into "smart" enterprises that create products that fully meet the needs of customers.

5. Opportunities should be created for scientists, engineers and constructors in our country to take their projects, inventions and developments to the world market in our country. Also, it is necessary to further develop the system of commercialization of the latest scientific ideas, to create the necessary conditions.

⁴Formed by the author based on the information of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan

6. In our country, he has proven himself in foreign experience We need to increase the level of use of the "cluster" system. Through this, the share of finished products in the products exported from our country will increase, costs related to logistics will decrease, and as a result, efficiency will increase.

By implementing the above and other measures, the development of innovative activities in our republic will increase the economic potential of our country. As a result, the standard of living of the population will increase.

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